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GIDROTEKNIKA INSHOOTLARINI LOYIHALASHDA YER SIRTI MURAKKABLIGINI BAXOLASH ALGORITMLARINI AVTOMATLASHTIRISH

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada gidrotexnik inshootlarni loyihalashda yer yuzasining murakkabligini baholash algoritmlarini avtomatlashtirish masalalari keltirilgan. Avtomatlashtirilgan loyihalash tizimlarida yaratilgan loyiha variantini qurish uchun yer yuzasining murakkablik darajasining topografik sirtlari nazariyasi asosida analitik usullarning algoritmlari ishlab chiqilgan. Umumiy topologiya usullari, tartibsiz sirtning nuqta turlari tavsiya etiladi. Geodeziya ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, har bir nuqta turi Gauss usullari bilan aniqlangan. Ishlab chiqilgan algoritmlar yer uchastkasini loyihalash va qurish jarayonlarining murakkablik darajasini aniqlashga xizmat qiladi.

Taklif etilayotgan algoritmlar hozirda mavjud dasturlash tillariga kiritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Topologik usullar, relyef, tartibsiz sirtlar, topografik sirtlar nazariyasi

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АВТОМАТИЗАЦИЯ АЛГОРИТМОВ ОЦЕНКИ СЛОЖНОСТИ ПОВЕРХНОСТИ ПРИ ПРОЕКТИРОВАНИИ ГИДРОТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ СООРУЖЕНИЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматриваются вопросы автоматизации алгоритмов оценки сложности земной поверхности при проектировании гидротехнических сооружений. Разработаны алгоритмы аналитических методов на основе теории топографических поверхностей уровня сложности земной поверхности для построения варианта проекта, созданного в автоматизированных системах проектирования. Рекомендованы методы общей топологии, типы точек неровной поверхности. По геодезическим данным каждый тип точки определялся гауссовыми методами. Разработанные алгоритмы служат для определения уровня сложности процессов проектирования и строительства земельных участков.

Предлагаемые алгоритмы включены в имеющиеся в настоящее время языки программирования.

Ключевые слова: Топологические методы, рельеф, нерегулярная поверхность, теория топографических поверхностей.

Ismatov BakhtiyorDoctoral student of National Research University
“Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers”.**AUTOMATION OF SURFACE COMPLEXITY ASSESSMENT ALGORITHMS WHEN
DESIGNING HYDROTECHNICAL CONSTRUCTIONS****ABSTRACT**

This article presents the issues of automating the algorithms for evaluating the complexity of the earth's surface in the design of hydrotechnical structures. Algorithms of analytical methods have been developed based on the theory of topographical surfaces of the complexity level of the earth's surface for the construction of the project variant created in automated project drafting systems. General topology methods, point types of irregular surface are recommended. According to geodetic data, each point type was determined by Gaussian methods. The developed algorithms serve to determine the level of complexity of land plot design and construction processes.

The proposed algorithms are included in currently available programming languages.

Key words: Topological methods, relief, irregular surface, theory of topographic surfaces

1 Introduction.

The role of hydrotechnical structures in the rational use of water resources for our republic is incomparable [1]. The water problem is becoming one of the urgent problems for our republic day by day. In this regard, scientific researches to determine the complexity of the earth's surface in the design of hydrotechnical structures are being carried out by the scientists of our Republic and abroad. Many types and projects of hydraulic structures are classified according to a number of the most common features. The development of algorithms and software packages for determining the level of complexity of the land in the process of project creation serves to increase the effectiveness of the project.

2 Methods.

During the project, foreign scientists conducted many scientific and practical studies on the automation of the process of determining the complexity of the earth's surface. Nguyen T.K. In the research work of the dissertation entitled “Research and development of a high-performance algorithm for creating digital terrain models”, the technology of effective creation of digital land models using points of different complexity of the terrain was developed in the design. The following results were achieved during the research work:

1. Methods of presentation and application of digital land models are reviewed and analyzed.
2. Algorithms of ascending and descending lines of points for construction of Delaunay triangulation are studied.
3. Algorithms of surface analysis have been studied.
4. Software for building digital terrain models with practical tools has been developed to implement the development of algorithms.

The process of creating a project is based on making the process more efficient and successful using special methods. The success of this process often depends on the experience of the designers and the methodologies used.

3 Result and Discussion.

Development and implementation of an automated software package based on the algorithms for evaluating the complexity of the earth's surface in drawing up project drawings of hydraulic engineering structures.

The process of drawing up project drawings of hydraulic engineering structures is based on a certain system of general algorithms. This process consists of several important stages, and each stage has specific goals and requirements.

1. Analysis of the topographical and seismological features of the area during the construction of the facility, as well as drawing up a map as a result of geodetic measurements, is one of the necessary steps to ensure the success of the project.

2. The process of creating contour lines of the relief zone is carried out in special computer programs based on the received coordinates. This process plays an important role in determining the shape and features of the relief.

3. Development of algorithms for evaluating the complexity of the earth's surface to create a design drawing of a hydrotechnical facility based on the obtained relief contours.

4. Based on the developed algorithms, it is introduced into a special JavaScript programming language to calculate the level of complexity of the land.

5. At the next stage, the visual appearance of the project is determined when the program creates a 3D surface of the earth.

It allows you to determine some coefficients that determine the level of complexity of the relief section. The choice of the step h is an important point in numerical differentiation problems, because errors in the values of the matrix terms strongly affect the result. Usually the step h is chosen as follows [2,3]:

$h = \left(\frac{3\Delta}{M}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$, where Δ is the absolute value of height values, M is a predetermined number.

Gaussian A square matrix ($A_{x,y}$) is defined.

$$A = \begin{vmatrix} \left[\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x^2}\right]_{ij} & \left[\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x \partial y}\right]_{ij} \\ \left[\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x \partial y}\right]_{ij} & \left[\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial y^2}\right]_{ij} \end{vmatrix} \quad (1)$$

its character reveals the type of elevation under investigation.

The following situations may occur:

$$A = \begin{vmatrix} -\left[\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x^2}\right]_{ij} & 0 \\ 0 & -\left[\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial y^2}\right]_{ij} \end{vmatrix} \neq 0 \quad (Ax, y) = -\lambda'x^2 - \lambda''y^2 \quad (2)$$

Altitude z_{ij} - is the main special point of type α_1 of the first order:

$$A = \begin{vmatrix} +\left[\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x^2}\right]_{ij} & 0 \\ 0 & +\left[\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial y^2}\right]_{ij} \end{vmatrix} \neq 0 \quad (Ax, y) = \lambda'x^2 + \lambda''y^2 \quad (3)$$

Altitude z_{ij} is the main special point of type β_1 of the first order:

$$A = \begin{vmatrix} +\left[\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x^2}\right]_{ij} & 0 \\ 0 & -\left[\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial y^2}\right]_{ij} \end{vmatrix} \neq 0 \quad (Ax, y) = \lambda'x^2 - \lambda''y^2 \quad (4)$$

z_{ij} - height is the main special point of type γ of the first order:

$$A = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (Ax, y) = 0 \tag{5}$$

Altitude z_{ij} is the main special point of type $\beta, \beta_2, \beta_3 \dots$ of the first order:

$$A = \begin{vmatrix} \pm \left[\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x^2} \right]_{ij} & \pm \left[\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x \partial y} \right]_{ij} \\ \pm \left[\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x \partial y} \right]_{ij} & \pm \left[\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial y^2} \right]_{ij} \end{vmatrix} \neq 0, (Ax, y) = \pm \lambda' x^2 \pm \lambda'' y^2 \pm \lambda''' yx \tag{6}$$

Height z_{ij} is a non-special point of type $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \gamma$ - with a set of secondary points, included in the maximum position of height z_{ij} .

Elektron hisoblash mashinasida moddiy o'zgaruvchan ma'lumotlarga ega bo'lgan haqiqiy ish sharoitida, nolga yaqin bo'lgan kichik lotin qiymatlari nol sifatida aniqlanadi [4,5].

In real working conditions with material variable data in an electronic calculator, small derivative values close to zero are defined as $\left[\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x_i \partial y_j} \right]_{i=1,2, j=1,2}$ zero [4,5].

Considering the high accuracy level of topographical photographs, i.e. 0.01 m, and with the help of which any area can be shown with a height difference of 1000 m, it can be said that the matrix analysis gives a true picture of the distribution of heights [6].

JavaScript is included in the programming language to easily implement the above algorithms. Figure 1-2 presents a software package that creates a 3D surface of the earth based on the points obtained with the help of geodetic data when drawing up a project drawing of hydrotechnical structures.

Figure 1. Earth's complexity index based on given x,y,z coordinates

Figure 2 3D surface complexity of the earth based on the given x,y,z coordinates

4. Conclusion.

In this article, a software package was created based on the algorithms for determining the complexity of the earth's surface in the design of hydrotechnical structures, and it can be used to show the complexity of the earth in various district projects. It is possible to determine the optimal area. Also, computer programs based on these algorithms can be used in the CAD system.

References

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6200 "On further improvement of the state management and control system in the use of water resources and measures to ensure the safety of water facilities" April 6, 2021, Tashkent city.
2. "Design of hydraulic structures" Bakiev M., Majidov I., Nosirov B., Khojakulov R., Saidov I. Publishing house "Fan and technology" Tashkent 2013. pp. 6-8.
3. Kashchenko N.A., Popov A.V. Geoinformation systems. Tutorial. Nizhny Novgorod, 2012. pp.15-16
4. Fox A., Pratt M. Computational geometry. Application in design and production. Moscow: Mir. 1982. 304 p.
5. Huaxing Lu, Modelling Terrain Complexity Research Gate, (2008): pp159-176
6. J. Schmidt, I.S. Evans, J. Brinkmann, Comparison of polynomial models for land surface curvature calculation/Int. J. Geogr Inf.Sci, (2003): pp797-814, V.17, #8

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